

Some common weed hosts of *Sarocladium oryzae* in Assam, India

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We observed severe sheath rot (ShR) symptoms on the common wetland weed, *Oryza rufipogon*, during a 1990 field survey in Jorhat district of Assam. We identified the causal organism to be *Sarocladium oryzae*, the incitant of rice ShR. The isolate reproduced the typical symptom on *O. rufipogon* and was found pathogenic to rice.

We carried out a pathogenicity test on 10 common ricefield weeds during the 1991 wet season to investigate the role of collateral hosts in perpetuating the pathogen. We inoculated weeds with an isolate from susceptible rice cultivar IR50 either by inserting an inoculum-

containing rice grain inside the uppermost leaf sheath or by spraying suspension after slightly injuring the plant (used where insertion of a grain was difficult).

Of the 10 weeds tested (see table), seven were successfully infected by the isolate. The remaining three did not exhibit any susceptible reaction even after repeated inoculations.

E. colona and *O. rufipogon* were the most susceptible because they produced symptoms the earliest (see table).

Pathogenicity tests using the fungus isolated from the artificially infected weeds gave positive results on IR50. A cross-inoculation test among the seven susceptible weeds with the pathogen was also successful with the symptoms being similar to those that develop when inoculated by rice isolates. These results, along with microscopic observation of the pathogen, confirmed the identity of *S. oryzae*. The results show that

Pathogenicity of *Sarocladium oryzae* on some weeds commonly found near ricefields.

Weed	Reaction ^a	Appearance of initial symptom (h after inoculation)
<i>Echinochloa colona</i> (L.) Link	+	72
<i>Monochoria vaginalis</i> (Bum. f.) Presl.	+	120
<i>Hymenachne assamica</i> (Hook f.) Hitchc.	+	168
<i>Leersia hexandra</i> Swartz.	+	144
<i>Panicum walense</i> Mez.	+	144
<i>Oryza rufipogon</i> Griff.	+	72
<i>Eleusine indica</i> (L.) Gaertn.	+	96
<i>Axonopus compressus</i> (Swartz.) Beauv.	-	
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L.) Pers.	-	
<i>Panicum notatum</i> Retz.	-	

^a+ = symptom appeared upon inoculation, - = did not appear upon inoculation.

H. assamica, *L. hexandra*, *P. walense*, and *O. rufipogon* are new weed hosts of the pathogen. □

Rice tungro disease (RTD) incidence in Assam, India

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RTD was first noticed in 1990 in about 100 ha of winter rice (Jul-Dec) in Kamrup and Nalbari districts. The incidence was moderate to severe, depending upon variety. Mashuri and a few traditional winter rice cultivars were severely affected. There had been no confirmed report of RTD in Assam up until then, although it

had probably been mistaken for Fe-induced yellowing, which is a major problem in the region.

An iodine test was used to narrow down the probable causes of yellowing. The veins of RTD-infected leaves turned black when dipped in tincture of iodine solution (1:4). Leaves with yellowing symptoms due to Fe toxicity did not turn black.

We conducted transmission tests of RTD samples collected from different sites to confirm the virus. About 50 viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* were confined to each sample for 48 h and then kept on 10-d-old healthy TN1 seedlings, at

2 insects/seedling, for 24 h. Typical symptoms of RTD developed after 10-15 d.

Leaf samples of selected disease isolates from TN1 were collected 30 d after incubation and homogenized with 0.02 M phosphate-buffered saline (pH 7.4). The extracts were indexed by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay using antisera obtained from IRRI. All of the isolates showed positive reaction to antisera of rice tungro bacilliform virus and rice tungro spherical virus, indicating that the samples were infected with both. This is the first confirmed report of RTD from this region. □

Integrated pest management—insects

Rice leaffolder (LF) outbreak in valleys of Uttar Pradesh (UP), India

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Cnaphalocrocis medinalis Guenée has become a serious rice pest under both irrigated transplanted and upland conditions in the hills of UP. During 1991 kharif (monsoon), a severe LF outbreak occurred in the irrigated valley regions of Almora district. We conducted an extensive survey during the cropping season to determine LF incidence.

In each of the surveyed valleys, we selected at random five ricefields of each variety and made observations at five randomly selected 1 m²-spots in each field. The plants in each spot were thoroughly screened for insects. We computed the ratio of infested plants to the number of plants sampled. The larvae collected from infested fields